

Abstract: *Fertility regulation is a high impact, cost effective health intervention used to prevent unwanted pregnancy. This study investigated Practices of Fertility Regulation Among Women of Childbearing age in South-South Nigeria .The objectives of the study were-to determine different practices of fertility regulation among women of childbearing age in South-South Nigeria and also to identify the factors influencing the utilization of fertility regulation among women of childbearing age in South-South Nigeria. Descriptive survey research design was adopted.845 women of child bearing age consituted the sample size, and the sampling method was multi -stage sampling technique. The instrument for data collection was questionnaire. Reliability of the instrument was ensured using a splint-half method of analysis. The used for data analysis was descriptive statistics of frequency and percentages while the stated hypotheses were tested at a significant level of 0.05 using Chi-square test. The findings were the -overall practice of fertility regulation was poor (36.6%). Also factors such religious beliefs, lack of partners support and myths and misconception of having male child as family representative continue to shape women fertility decision.Results from the hypotheses showed that there was no significant association between high parity and fertility regulation among childbearing women in South-South Nigeria, there was no significant association between the religious belief of women and the use of fertility regulation,also there was no significant association between the determinant of fertility regulation and it's use among women of childbearing age in South-South Nigeria.Recommendations included need for comprehensive fertility education campaign that aim to debunk myth and misconception surrounding contraception and also to involve men on fertility regulation services in order to have full support of their partners and thereby increasing the practices of fertility regulation accessibility.*

Key words: Fertility regulations, childbearing women, practices

Introduction

Fertility indicates the product or output of reproduction (Aldo, 2021). Fertility trends in most of the developed world in the late 1990s showed a substantial decline to two children or fewer from the traditional six children per woman (Oluweyemisi, Alaba, Olusanya, Olubusoye and Olaca, 2017). The total fertility rate is declining globally, but it is decreasing more slowly in Sub-Sahara Africa with a total rate of 4.69 children per woman in 2018, down from 5.37 in 2008 (Singh, Darroch and Ashford, 2014). Most African countries lack demography and population policy to control or monitor fertility rates despite declining in natural resources, lack of infrastructure such as housing, school, health facilities and increased unemployment (Tamirat, Tesema and Tessama, 2021). Among Sub-Saharan African countries, Nigeria is generally known as the most populous country in Africa with a population of over 174 million in 2013, which is approximately one-sixth of the total African population (Kazembe, 2019).

Fertility is the major determinant of high population growth and on a large scale, population growth could hinder a country's economic performance as this may put pressure on the already limited infrastructure and government funds (Ahinkorah, Seidu and Armah-Anseh, 2021). Many households with smaller family sizes are more likely to benefit from demographic dividends and this suggests that uncontrolled population growth will have some dire consequences on the economic status as well as other devastating effects on maternal and child health (Ahinkorah et al, 2021). High fertility coupled with

high population growth may lead to increase in maternal and pediatric diseases and mortality (Skiröekk, 2018). A high fertility rate, which is 5.0 or higher, is characterized among others by health risks for children and their mothers as well as food insecurity (Skiröekk, 2018). Considerable evidence from economically advanced countries indicate that reduced fertility rates foster economic development and social well-being of the citizens (Ahinkorah, Seidu and Armah-Arseh, 2021).

Fertility level is undoubtedly conditioned by the cultural, health, political, demographic and socioeconomic setting (Kazembe, 2019). Proximate and socio-demographic determinants of fertility such as current marital status, polygamy, age at first marriage, first sexual intercourse and recent sexual activity, postpartum amenorrhea, abstinence as well as use of contraceptives, education, place of residence and wealth index have been found to significantly affect fertility patterns (Skiröekk, 2018). According to the 2013 Nigeria Demographic Health Survey, one in ten pregnancies in Nigeria were either mistimed or not wanted (Roshid, 2015; Kazembe, 2019). Yet, about 16% of married women who want to stop or postpone childbearing in Nigeria are currently not using any form of contraception (Babalola, Oyemibi and Speizer, 2017). This unmet need for contraception is even higher amongst unmarried, sexually active women (22%) (Skiröekk, 2018). If all women who wanted to delay or stop childbirth use effective contraception to prevent unintended pregnancy, maternal death would decline by 67% and newborn death would decline by 77% (Kazembe, 2019). Family planning is a high impact, cost-effective health intervention that could save numerous lives, especially in developing countries (Darroch and Ashford, 2019).

There have been methods of fertility regulation at least as far back as the beginnings of recorded history, as families have sought to control the number and timing of births (Alkema, et al 2016). Male methods of family planning can range from a barrier method such as the condom, or withdrawal, or the surgical procedure of vasectomy. Female methods include the oral contraceptive pill or the barrier method of the female condom and use of implants. Extended breastfeeding of the previous infant has long been known to suppress ovulation and enable spacing between births. Social concerns regarding birth and reproduction vary internationally, with age, ethnic identity, or religion (Aldo, 2021). Cultural factors, such as assuring virginity of marriageable females in some societies, religious opposition to fertility regulation in others, or in a few societies, female genital surgery for removal of the clitoris to reduce female enjoyment of sexual relations, have impact on quality of life as well as reproductive capacity (Alkema, et al, 2016).

The practice of contraceptives and fertility regulations has been found to be beneficiary to couples, but most women may or may not be in support of such practice (Aldo, 2021). It will be revealing therefore to know the behaviour of women towards fertility regulations. It is against this background that the researchers were motivated to investigate practices of fertility regulation among women of childbearing age in South-South Nigeria.

Research Questions

1. What are the practices among women of childbearing age on fertility regulations in South -South Nigeria
2. What are the factors influencing the utilization of fertility regulations among women of childbearing age in South -South Nigeria

Research Hypotheses

1. There would be no significant association between high parity and fertility regulation among women of childbearing age in South -South Nigeria.
2. There would be no significant association between religious beliefs of women of childbearing age and their fertility regulation in South -South Nigeria.
3. There would be no significant association between determinants of fertility regulation and practice of fertility regulations among women of childbearing age in South South Nigeria

Materials and Methods

Research Design

The study adopted a cross-sectional design.

Sample Size

A sample of 845 women of childbearing age (15-49 years) in the South-South region was selected from the healthcare facilities across the states in the South-South region of Nigeria.

Instrument for Data Collection

The instrument titled *Questionnaire on Practices of Fertility Regulation Among Women of Childbearing Age (QPRAWA)* was utilized by the researcher for the study. The QPRAWCA was adapted by the researcher from instruments on *Demographic Health and Survey (DHS)* program by USAID (2023), *Fertility and Family Survey (FFS)* by the United Nations Economic Commission for Europe (UNECE), and *BioMed Centre (BMC), as well as Pregnancy and Childbirth* by the Current Scientific Survey group (2013). QPRAWCA is divided into six sections, Section A required respondents to provide their demographic information, such as age, marital status, educational level, occupation, income level and contraceptive use.

Section B: comprises 12 items on different practices of fertility regulation, Section C: 12 items on factors influencing the utilization of fertility regulations. The items in the questionnaire were rated on a four-point scale: Strongly Agree (SA)=4, Agree (A)=3, Disagree (D)=2, Strongly Disagree (SD)=1; as well as Yes or No options with 1 point for each Yes or No response.

Reliability of the Instrument

The reliability of the instrument was conducted using 10% of the sample size which was 84 women of childbearing age. Split-half method of analysis was adopted in testing the reliability of the instrument. Pearson Product Moment correlation was used to determine the degree between the results obtained from the subset. A reliability coefficient of 0.989 obtained indicating a high level of reliability in the questionnaire's results.

Ethical Consideration

To ensure the ethical conduct of the research, the researchers applied and obtained approval from the Ethics Committee of all the States under study (Akwa-Ibom, Delta, Rivers, Bayelsa, Cross River, Edinburg State). All the respondents were informed about the purpose and nature of the study, as well as their rights to withdraw at any time without penalty. Informed consent was obtained from the respondents and confidentiality was maintained for all information obtained from the respondents.

Method of Data Collection

The researchers obtained permission from the management of the selected primary, secondary and tertiary healthcare facilities to gain access to the respondents, and with their permission, the researchers approached women of childbearing age attending the healthcare facilities in the family planning units on the clinic days of the various facilities.

To facilitate the collection of data, the researchers recruited trained research assistants, two for each facility who assisted the researcher, in administering copies of the questionnaire to the respondents across different selected healthcare facilities in the South-South region of Nigeria. The research assistants were briefed on how to administer and retrieve the questionnaire to ensure consistency in data collection and to minimize potential bias.

A total of 845 copies of the questionnaire were administered to the respondents. The completed questionnaire were collected on a spot. For those who agreed to respond at later dates, the researchers revisited them on the agreed dates to ensure a 100% response rate to the instrument. 845 copies of the instrument were administered to the respondents and same number were returned giving 100% return rate.

Method of Data Analysis

The demographic data were analysed using frequency and percentages. Weighted mean and percentages were used to answer the research questions, while Chi-Square was used to test all the hypotheses at the 0.05 level of significance. The acceptable meaning score was minimum of 2.5. Any score below 2.5 was rejected. Percentage score of 50% and above the "yes" response was deemed positive for the relevant research question. Any "yes" response below 50% was deemed negative

Results

Table 1 demographic distribution of the respondents (N=845)

Variable	Frequency (n=845)	Percentage (%)
State of origin		
Akwa-Ibom	150	17.75
Bayelsa	51	6.04
Cross Rivers	70	8.28
Delta	200	23.67
Edo	76	8.99
Rivers	298	35.27
Health Facility		
Primary	289	34.20
Secondary	250	29.59
Tertiary	306	36.21
Ownership of health Facility		
Government	434	51.36
Private	411	48.64
Religion		
Christianity	599	70.89
Islam	120	14.20
Traditional	126	14.91
Residence		
RURAL	386	45.68
URBAN	459	54.32
Age at last birthday		
18-25	603	71.36
26-35	120	14.20
36 – Above	122	14.44
Marital Status		
Married	459	54.32
Single	386	45.68
Widowed	0	-
Divorced	0	-
Separated	0	-
Educational Level		
Primary	289	34.20
Secondary	250	29.59
Tertiary	306	36.21
Employment Status		
Employed	489	57.87
Unemployed	356	42.13
How many children have you had		
1-3	289	34.20
4-5	250	29.59
6-Above	306	36.21
Total	845	100.0

Table 1 shows that majority of the respondents from Rivers State, comprising 35.27% followed by Delta State with 23.67%. Akwa Ibom accounted for 17.75%, while Cross Rivers, Edo, and Bayelsa states contributed 8.28%, 8.99%, and 6.04%, respectively. 36.21%, utilized tertiary healthcare facilities, while 34.20% attended primary healthcare centers, and 29.59% used secondary healthcare services. In terms of ownership, the facilities were split between government-owned institutions, which served 51.36% of the women, and private facilities, which catered for 48.64%.

The table shows that the respondents were Christian, with 70.89% . Islam was practiced by 14.20% of the respondents, while 14.91% practiced traditional religions. The table also showed that 54.32% of the women resides in urban areas and 45.68% in rural settings.

The age distribution indicated that a majority of the respondents, 71.36%, were between the ages of 18 and 25. Women aged 26 to 35 constituted 14.20%, while those aged 36 and above accounted for 14.44%. Marital status showed 54.32% of the women were married, while 45.68% were single.

Educational attainment varied among the women surveyed. Tertiary education was the most common, with 36.21% having attained this level, followed by 34.20% with primary education and 29.59% with secondary education. Employment status was also examined, revealing that 57.87% of the respondents were self-employed, while 42.13% were unemployed. Family parity among the respondents showed that 36.21% had six or more children, while 34.20% had between one and three children. Women with four to five children made up 29.59% of the sample.

Research Question one

What are the practices among women of childbearing age on fertility regulations in South-South Nigeria?

Table 2 shows practices among women of childbearing age on fertility regulations in South -South Nigeria

Practices	Yes (%)	No (%)	Total N %	Remark
Do you practice fertility regulation?	309(36.6)	536(63.4)	845(100%)	Negative
Do you adhere to any specific religion?	339 (40.1)	506 (59.9)	845(100%)	Positive
Is your religion against contraception?	240 (28.4)	605 (71.6)	845(100%)	Positive
Have you ever used contraceptives to prevent pregnancy when not needed?	274 (32.4)	571 (67.6)	845(100%)	Negative
Is your partner using any contraceptives to prevent pregnancy occurrence currently?	305 (36.1)	540 (63.9)	845(100%)	Negative
Did you have any operation for contraceptives or medical reasons?	289 (34.2)	556 (65.8)	845(100%)	Negative
Is there any particular method or combination of methods that you/or your partner have relied on for contraceptive purposes?	405 (47.9)	440 (52.1)	845(100%)	Negative

Which contraceptive methods or combinations of methods have you relied on	Total No	%	Remark
Diaphragm	201	(23.8)	644 (76.2) 845(100%) Negative
Pills	168	(19.9)	677 (80.1) 845(100%) Negative
Foam	240	(28.4)	605 (71.6) 845(100%) Negative

IUCD	274	(32.4)	571	(67.6)	845(100%)	Negative
Jelly	305	(36.1)	540	(63.9)	845(100%)	Negative
Sterilization	289	(34.2)	556	(65.8)	845(100%)	Negative
Sponge	110	(13.0)	735	(87.0)	845(100%)	Negative
Periodic abstinence	206	(24.4)	639	(75.6)	845(100%)	Negative
Safe period	311	(36.8)	534	(63.2)	845(100%)	Negative
Withdrawal	405	(47.9)	440	(52.1)	845(100%)	Negative
Any other methods	-					
In what age did you first start use contraceptives?						
10-20	105	(12.4)	740	(87.6)	845(100%)	Negative
21-30	92	(10.9)	753	(89.1)	845(100%)	Negative
31 -40	128	(15.1)	717	(84.9)	845(100%)	Negative
41-50	256	(30.3)	589	(69.7)	845(100%)	Negative
Are you currently still using any type of contraceptive method?						
If No, why did you stop?	-					
Method failed	293	(34.7)	552	(65.3)	845(100%)	Negative
Pregnancy occurred	682	(80.7)	163	(19.3)	845(100%)	Negative
Cost	384	(45.4)	461	(54.6)	845(100%)	Negative
Wanted child	284	(33.6)	561	(66.4)	845(100%)	Negative
Unwelcoming attitude of staff	309	(36.6)	536	(63.4)	845(100%)	Negative
Partner disapproved	262	(31.0)	583	(69.0)	845(100%)	Negative
Side effects	161	(19.1)	684	(80.9)	845(100%)	Negative
Health concern	622	(73.6)	223	(26.4)	845(100%)	Negative
No access/Unavailability	366	(43.3)	479	(56.7)	845(100%)	Negative
Wanted other method	274	(32.4)	571	(67.6)	845(100%)	Negative
Inconvenient to use	295	(34.9)	550	(65.1)	845(100%)	Negative
No sexual relation	167	(19.8)	678	(80.2)	845(100%)	Negative
Overall/Average score for practice of Fertility regulation	309.	(36.6%)	536	(63.4)	845(100%)	Negative

Table 2 shows that 63.4%, reported that they do not practice fertility regulation, while only 36.6% stated that they do. Regarding religious adherence, 40.1% of the respondents identified with religion, while 59.9% did not indicate adherence. Among those who practice religious belief 28.4% reported that their faith is against contraception, whereas 71.6% stated that their religion does not oppose using contraception. 32.4% of the respondents admitted to having used contraceptives to prevent pregnancy when it was not needed, while 67.6% had never done so. 36.1% reported that their partners were currently using contraceptive methods, whereas 63.9% said their partners were not.

Surgical interventions for contraceptive or medical reasons were reported by 34.2% of the respondents, while 65.8% had not undergone any such procedure. Additionally, 47.9% indicated that they or their partners relied on a specific contraceptive method or a combination of methods, while 52.1% did not.

Among the different contraceptive methods, withdrawal was the most commonly used, with 47.9% of respondents reporting having relied on it at some point. Other frequently used methods included the safe period (36.8%), jelly (36.1%), and sterilization (34.2%). The intrauterine device (IUD) was used by 32.4% of the respondents, while periodic abstinence was reported by 24.4%. The least frequently used method was the sponge, with 13.0% of respondents having used it. Pills, foam, and diaphragms were used by 19.9%, 28.4%, and 23.8% of respondents, respectively.

Regarding the age at which contraceptive use began, the majority of respondents initiated contraceptive use between the ages of 41 and 50, representing 30.3% of the sample. This was followed by 15.1% who began using contraception between 31 and 40 years, 12.4% between 10 and 20 years, and 10.9% between 21 and 30 years. When asked about the reasons for discontinuation, the most common response was pregnancy occurrence, with 80.7%. Health concerns were another factor, accounting for 73.6%. Cost also played a role, of 45.4% to discontinue use.

Some respondents stopped using contraceptives because they found the method inconvenient to use (34.9%) or wanted a different contraceptive method (32.4%). Partner disapproval influenced discontinuation in 31.0% of cases, while an unwelcoming attitude from healthcare staff was reported by 36.6%. Additionally, 43.3% mentioned unavailability or lack of access as a reason for stopping contraception. Side effects were cited by 19.1% of respondents, while 19.8% stopped using contraceptives because they were no longer in sexual relation. Overall result of practice of fertility regulation was negative (poor) = 36.6%

Research Question Two

What are the factors influencing Utilization of fertility regulation among women of childbearing age in South -South Nigeria?

Table 3 Factors influencing the utilization of fertility regulation among women of childbearing age in South-South Nigeria.

Items	SA 4	A 3	D 2	SD 1	Total No	Total Point	Mean	Remark
Men are the decision makers for the utilization of contraceptives, my partners does not want me access fertility regulations services.	260(30.8)	185(21.9)	266(31.5)	134(15.9)	845	2261	2.68	Accepted
Considering the economic status, I cannot afford the cost of fertility regulations.	149(17.6)	266(31.5)	231(27.3)	199(23.6)	845	2055	2.43	rejected
Fertility regulation can render me infertile, having difficulty for the next conception.	166(19.6)	238(28.2)	261(30.9)	80(21.3)	845	2080	2.5	Accepted

I don't want fertility regulations services because of fear of its side effects.	217(25.7)	254(30.1)	227(26.9)	147(17.4)	845	2231	2.64	Accepted
The myths and misconceptions about contraceptives make me avoid it.	251(29.7)	276(32.7)	236(27.9)	82(9.7)	845	2386	2.82	Accepted
The health facilities are inaccessible, there are no good roads, no transportation.	129(15.3)	202(23.9)	267(31.6)	247(29.2)	845	1903	2.25	rejected
Each time I go for fertility regulations services, the nurse will say the commodities are unavailable, and the government will not supply.	94(11.1)	141(16.7)	126(14.9)	484(57.3)	845	1544	1.83	rejected
I stopped accessing fertility regulations due to the unwelcoming attitude of health workers in the family planning unit.	165(19.5)	229(27.1)	273(32.3)	178(21.1)	845	2071	2.5	Accepted
My religion is against using contraceptives.	132(15.6)	340(40.2)	113(13.4)	260(30.8)	845	2034	2.41	rejected
I believe contraceptives is for elderly women that must have completed their family size and not for younger couples like me.	231(27.3)	344(40.7)	143(16.9)	127(15.0)	845	2369	2.8	Accepted
Contraceptives has failed my neighbor so I see it as being ineffective.	144(17.0)	329(38.9)	149(17.6)	223(26.4)	845	2084	2.5	Accepted
I stopped accessing contraceptives because the staff I met are not qualified, beings bics in the way they render services.	99(11.7)	341(40.4)	118(13.9)	287(33.9)	845	1942	2.3	Rejected
Overall mean score							2.47	Rejected

The results in table 3 highlighted various factors influencing the utilization of fertility regulation among women of childbearing age in South-South Nigeria. A key finding was that decision-making regarding contraceptive use is often controlled by men, as many women reported that their partners did not support their access to fertility regulation services. This factor was strongly acknowledged, with a mean score of 2.68.

Economic constraints also play a role, as some women expressed concerns about the affordability of the cost of fertility regulation services with a mean score of 2.43. Additionally, fears of infertility resulting from contraceptive use had a mean score of 2.5. Fear of side effects emerged as another major concern, with a mean score of 2.64. Also myths and misconceptions about contraception had mean score of 2.82.

Access to facilities had mean score of 2.25 while availability of commodities in different facilities has mean score of 1.83. Unwelcoming attitude of health workers had mean score of 2.5, while religious belief against fertility regulation is 2.41 and the belief that fertility regulation is only for the elderly who must have completed their family size had mean score of 2..8.

Additionally perception that contraceptives has failed others thus seen as ineffective had mean score of 2.5 while concern over the perceived lack of qualified staff among service providers were expressed with mean score of 2.3. The overall mean score was 2.47 which indicate negative score.

Research Hypothesis one

There would be no significant association between high parity and fertility regulation among women of childbearing age in south -south Nigeria.

Table 4 *Chisquare result on the association between high parity and fertility regulation among women of childbearing age in South-South Nigeria.*

	Sum of squares	df	Mean square	X ²	Sig
Fertility Regulation	15.586	8	1.948	608.847	.051
High Parity	.003	1	.003		
Total	15.590	9			

The result from the chisquare test in Table 4 was used to assess the association between high parity and fertility regulation among women of childbearing age in South-South Nigeria. The p-value of 0.051 is more than the 0.05 significance level, which leads us to accept the null hypothesis. This suggests that there is no significant association between high parity and fertility regulation among childbearing women in South-South Nigeria.

Research Hypothesis Two

There would be no significant association between the religious beliefs of women of childbearing age in South -South Nigeria.

Table 5 *Chisquare result on the association between the religious beliefs of women of child bearing age and fertility regulation in South South Nigeria.*

	Sum of squares	Df	Mean square	X ²	Sig
Fertility Regulation	.329	6	.055	608.847	.061
Religious belief	.000				
Total	.329	6			

The Chisquare result in Table 5 was used to examine the association between the religious beliefs of women of childbearing age and fertility regulation in South-South Nigeria. The p-value of 0.061 is more than the 0.05 significance level, indicating that we accept the null hypothesis. This suggests that there is no significant association between the religious beliefs of women and their use of fertility regulation.

Research Hypothesis Three

There would be no significant association between determinants of fertility regulation and practice of fertility regulation among women of childbearing age in South -South Nigeria.

Table 6 Chisquare result on the association between determinants of fertility regulation and practice of fertility regulation among women of childbearing in South -South Nigeria

	Sum of squares	df	Mean square	x	Sig
Fertility Regulation	.045	8	.006	37.368	.056
Determinant factors	.003	3	.000		
Total	.450	11			

The Chisquare result in Table 6 was used to test the association between the determinants of fertility regulation and practices of fertility regulation among women of childbearing age in South-South Nigeria. The p-value of 0.056 is more than the 0.05 significance level, indicating that the null hypothesis is accepted. This suggests that there is no significant association between the determinants of fertility regulation and its practice among omen of childbearing age in South -South Nigeria.

Discussion of Findings

Research Question 1: To determine practices of fertility regulations among women of childbearing age in South-South Nigeria.

The result of the findings in table 2 showed that a total average score of 36.6% was obtained on practices of fertility regulations. This provides insight into the practices regarding the fertility regulation services among women of childbearing age in south-south Nigeria The result of the findings showed that average score for practice of fertility regulation was poor.

The findings in this study is in line with the study conducted by Ambareen, Halenma, Hashmi, and Zehra, (2018) on awareness and practice of contraceptives among women of childbearing age in 3 selected primary health centers in Lagos, Nigeria which showed that more than 80% of women were aware of fertility regulations but only 40% practiced it.

Isu and Palpanadan (2020) in their own study also reported negative result. Their own study showed that out of the 609 respondents, 20% of the women of childbearing age practice combined natural and calendar method of fertility regulations, while 50% of the women were not using any type of fertility regulation indicating that practices of fertility regulation was extremely low among women in Bangladesh.

Research Question 2: To identify the factors influencing the utilization of fertility regulation among women of childbearing age in south-south, Nigeria.

The result of the findings in table 3 shows a total average mean score of 2.47. for the factors influencing the use of utilization of fertility among women of childbearing age in south-south, Nigeria. It is evident that some of the factors that some sex partners do not want their partners to access fertility regulation services (table 3).. This suggests that there is a general dislike of fertility regulation services by some sex partners. Economic constraints also play a role in fertility regulation accessibility with low mean score of 2.43. Thirdly, fear of side effects emerged as another major concern with mean score of 2.64 suggesting that apprehension about potential side effects discourages many women from using contraceptives.

Myths and misconceptions about contraceptives were wildly accepted as a factor preventing usage with highest mean score 2.82. Furthermore, inaccessibility of health facilities evident mean score of 2.25 while availability of commodity indicates low mean score of 1.83.

More so, unwelcoming attitude of health workers has mean score of 2.5, while cultural/religion belief against fertility regulation is 2.41 and the belief that fertility regulation is only for the elderly who must have completed their family size has mean score of 2.8 Additionally, perception that contraceptives has failed, others thus seen as effective has mean score of 2•5 while concern over the perceived lack of qualified staff among service providers were expressed with mean score of 2.3.

The current findings is not in line with the study by Akpan and ITA(2015),on the factors influencing utilization of fertility regulation among women of childbearing age in Akwa-Ibom State. The result revealed that the major factors influencing utilization of fertility regulation is marital duration and

ethnicity while the current study reported myths and misconception (2.8) as the major factor influencing fertility regulation utilization.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant association between high parity and fertility regulations among women of childbearing age in south-south, Nigeria.

The results in table 4 were indicating the association between high parity and fertility regulation using chi-square test. The p-value of 0.051 is more than the 0.05 significance level. This suggests that there was no significant association between high parity and fertility regulation among women of childbearing age in south-south, Nigeria.

The finding is in line with the finding by Akachukwu (2016) on his investigations on how childbearing women perceive their fertility status /birth order in Kogi State. The study indicated that majority of the childbearing women had high parity despite their knowledge on fertility status and fertility regulation. The decision-making concerning fertility regulation acceptance was mostly done at home. The major reason for assessing contraception is to space children rather than having few children.

Hypothesis 2:

There would be no significant association between religious beliefs of women of childbearing age and fertility regulation in south-south, Nigeria. The chi-square result in table 5 indicated p-value of 0.061 greater than 0.05 significance level. This suggests that there is no significant association between religious beliefs of women of childbearing age in south-south, Nigeria and their use of fertility regulation. This finding was not in line with findings by the Lashkarian and Molevalli (2020) who investigated factors influencing the utilization of fertility regulation among women of childbearing age. Their result showed that religious beliefs and tradition are factors influencing the utilization among women of childbearing age. Also the findings by Mustus (2018) indicated that religious affiliation is a factor.

Hypothesis 3:

There would be no significant association between determinants of fertility regulation and practices of fertility regulation among women of childbearing age in south-south, Nigeria. The p-value of 0.056 was more than the 0.05 significance level. This suggests that there is no significant association between the determinants of fertility regulation and its practices among women of childbearing age in south-south, Nigeria. Kenneth (2019) investigated on the factors influencing fertility regulations among women of childbearing age in Tanzania's rural lake zone using eight Focal group of childbearing women and the partner support was seen as the major hindrances to fertility regulations acceptance.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the study highlights the practices and factors influencing fertility regulation among women of childbearing age in South-South Nigeria showing that Lack of partner support continue to shape women's fertility decisions. The preference for large families, particularly for male children, remains a strong cultural norm, while misconceptions about contraception, particularly regarding its use and effectiveness, persist. There were no significant associations between high parity, religion and determinants of fertility regulation of the childbearing women respectively with their fertility regulation practices

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